

Название публикации: «**PSYCHOLOGY AND TECHNICAL PROGRESS**»

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Annotation: Science and technology are central to nearly all areas of human endeavor. The study of science and technology is evident in disciplines such as philosophy of science, philosophy of technology, sociology of knowledge, and history of science and technology, as well as in interdisciplinary research such as science and technology. Until now, psychology has remained marginal in this space.

We argue that this is partly due to the fact that psychology views itself as a science (not an object of study). It is also the result of previous attempts at the development

of psychology, science and technology clearly adhere to a narrow epistemological position that contradicts the broader epistemic basis of research in science and technology and related fields.

Keywords: science, technology, psychology, research.

XX century production, new types of equipment, communication

It is characterized by the rapid growth of vehicles, the introduction of electronics, automation, the adoption of new, faster forms of transport. All this puts great demands on the human psyche. In modern industry, transport and the military, it is necessary to take into account psychological factors, such as human capabilities, cognitive processes - perception, memory, thinking, personality traits - character, temperament, speed of reactions, etc. In today's fast-paced aircraft, people working in the operational and control areas of a huge electrical system have to make a quick

decision in a very short time, otherwise it can lead to accidents. Psychology has important requirements in determining whether people have the ability to work in such a complex environment, and whether the link is suitable or not. Scientific and technological progress in industrial and agro-industrial production, transport, energy and other industries is constantly accompanied by a continuous increase in the role of man as a subject of labor in achieving high efficiency and quality of activity. At the same time, modern production makes ever new and rapidly growing demands not only on various machines and equipment in general, but above all on the workers themselves, on the person. It is man who creates these machines, manages and exploits this technique. This means that for the development of modern production on a scientific basis and to ensure the necessary efficiency of the operation of machines, the need arose to coordinate the capabilities of technology and the characteristics of a person involved in the production process. The study of the psychological capabilities of a person in connection with the requirements imposed on him by complex types of labor activity characterizes the important role of modern psychology.

Engineering psychology, which deals with the solution of the "man-machine" problem (issues of interaction between man and technology), as well as labor psychology in general, is in close contact with many branches of technology.

There is another side to the issue, and that is the issue of how to improve and adapt to the capabilities of the person who "communicates" with complex techniques and machines at a time when technology is advancing. Especially for an independent Uzbekistan, which knows the secrets of complex modern technology, how important

it is to provide services to the development of society and science, it is necessary to adapt the minds, thinking and abilities of every ordinary citizen to this technology.

“It is very important to find the most effective ways of dialogue. Success in the

training of qualified specialists who are comfortable with technology can be achieved only if they use the methods of technical sciences, pedagogy and psychology. The further development of psychology is significantly influenced by the computer revolution.

A number of functions that were considered a unique property of human consciousness - the functions of accumulating and processing information, control and monitoring - began to be performed by electronic devices. The use of information-theoretic concepts and models contributed to the introduction of new logical and mathematical methods into psychology. At the same time, individual researchers, intoxicated by the successes of cybernetics, began to interpret a person as an automaton with programmed control. At the same time, automation and cybernation have sharply increased the interest in the study and effective use of functions that cannot be transferred by an electronic device, primarily creativity. For the future of humanity, for the individual and his mental structure, the significance of the computer revolution is enormous. But no matter how a person's personality changes, no matter what miracles electronic information technology has created, it will still have mental properties with all the signs inherent in the subject of psychology.

Engineering psychology is the study of the relationship between man and technology, which is inextricably linked with many areas of technology, such as bionics and cyber ethics. It should be noted that in recent years the interest in this area in our country has grown significantly. That is why a number of young, talented

specialists are conducting research in the field of engineering psychology.

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